

Photon-counting super-sampled imaging using piezoelectric motors

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Abstract: Spatial resolution and dose efficiency are crucial in radiographic imaging. This project explores resolution enhancement using super-sampling with photon-counting detectors (PCD) equipped with high-Z sensors. These spectroscopic X-ray detectors promise to transform radiographic and CT imaging, aiming to improve future pre-clinical and clinical applications. A PCD-based micro-CT system was modified for piezo-driven super-sampling (SS). Precise image registration and iterative deconvolution techniques were used. Resolution was measured using a slanted edge and a bar pattern phantom. While artifacts due to sensor inhomogeneities were noted, a threefold improvement in spatial resolution was achieved.

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I. Introduction

Spatial resolution and dose efficiency are key criteria in radiographic imaging. The current project investigates super-sampling (SS) resolution enhancement utilizing photon-counting detectors (PCDs) equipped with high-Z sensors which are gaining relevance for radiographic and computed tomography (CT) imaging.

Photon-counting detector (PCD) technology has brought about a significant advancement in X-ray imaging, enhancing image clarity while lowering radiation exposure for patients [1]. PCDs differ from traditional energy-integrating detectors (EIDs) by their ability to discriminate photon energies, reducing detector noise and heightening signal clarity by setting energy thresholds above the innate noise levels of the detectors [1]. The benefits of PCDs are based on their mechanism of direct signal detection, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Respective schematics of signal acquisition in scintillator-based, energy-integrating detectors (EIDs, left), and direct-converting, photon-counting detectors (PCDs, right)

The steep edge response of pixels in PCDs indicates a strong potential for resolution enhancement through super-sampled image acquisition. This allows to overcome the fabrication-dependent pixel size limits of current PCDs, while maintaining high photon efficiency [2].

Fig. 2: The graph of Maneuski et al. shows the response of the pixels in a PCD determined by evaluating the detector counts of the individual pixel as a function of the position of an X-ray micro beam [2]

II. Material and methods

This work builds on an approach originally published by Irani et al. [3]. Utilizing image correlation to determine the sampling shift compensates for irregular super-sampling motion, including influences like thermal drift.

An existing imaging system, featuring a prototype DECTRIS Santis GaAs detector, was modified to allow for piezo-driven super-sampling. Image reconstruction was performed utilizing a modification of a custom iterative reconstruction routine, originally designed for CT reconstruction. A particular benefit of the utilized reconstruction tool is the employed distance-driven ray tracer [4], assuming a box-shaped response function for the detector, which reflects the observed behavior of PCDs well (see Figure 2) [5].

To assess the resolution enhancement, a slanted tungsten edge and a bar pattern phantom were imaged. The edge spread function (ESF) was calculated from the slanted edge measurement according to Zhang et al. [6]. Sampling

movement covered a total range of 1.5 by 1.5 pixels, with 21 x 21 sub-steps for both objects.

The bar pattern phantom includes point and bar patterns from 150 μm down to 5 μm , which are used to visualize the resolution improvements achieved by utilizing SS.

III. Results and discussion

Figure 3 compares processing approaches for the super-sampled slanted edge phantom (a) and the resulting edge spread functions (b). The average edge response in native pixel resolution is indicated in blue. The pixel grid was upsampled by 12 x 12 in reconstruction, resulting in 144 sub-pixels per detector element. The native ESF is shown in orange. The green ESF represents the super-sampled measurement using the iterative deconvolution approach.

Fig. 3: (a): measurements of the slanted edge phantom with different processing methods. (b): resulting Edge spread function (ESF) of the imaging system using a Dectris Santis GaAs 750 μm ; average pixel response in blue, native ESF in orange, and iterative reconstruction in green.

The 10% and 90% intercepts are used to quantify the resolution gain. A width of 15 subpixels or 93.75 μm is found for the native ESF, whereas the width using iterative deconvolution is 5 subpixels or 31.25 μm , indicating a 3-fold resolution enhancement. The mean pixel signal at the edge is plotted in blue for reference.

Figure 4 compares the radiography of the micro-CT bar pattern phantom with and without SS. Whereas the resolution appears strongly enhanced in the latter, distortions that become visible at the higher resolution are illustrated in the results without (a) and with the SS (b). The comparison focusing on the visible evaluation of the resolution between (a) and (b) is shown in the orange box in Figure 4. The bar and point patterns that are visible in the image using SS (b) have a width of 20 μm and 25 μm . Without SS (a), the bar pattern is not resolved.

This demonstrates the improvement of resolution using SS. Furthermore, due to the enhanced resolution, sensor inhomogeneities become visible in the acquired image. In addition, the line pattern is distorted (see yellow box Figure 4), which is probably caused by an “electrostatic lensing effect” in the sensor material (GaAs).

Fig. 4: Comparison of measured images of the bar pattern phantom without (a) and with super-sampling (b), acquired with the same photon statistics: (a) 441 (21x21) projections acquired without displacement are averaged; (b) super-sampling is performed by acquiring the same amount of projections as for (a) at different sub-pixel displacements, followed by iterative image reconstruction. The orange box (1), compares the resolution of 20 μm and 25 μm patterns. In the yellow box (2) distortions of a bar pattern due to sensor material inhomogeneities are visible. The blue box (3) displays some ringing artifacts likely caused by the deconvolution algorithm, also visible in the ESF (Fig. 3).

IV. Conclusions

It has been shown that photon-counting radiographic image resolution can be substantially enhanced by sub-pixel stepping using piezo-driven super-sampling in combination with iterative deconvolution techniques. Additional benefits could be gained by increasing the motion range to cover several pixels, as the averaging effect would reduce the influence of inter-pixel response variations.

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